

Studies on *s*-Triazines. Part-II. Preparation of 2,4-Diaryl-amino-6-carbethoxymethylamino and 4-(2',4'-Diarylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)aminoantipyrine

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Manuscript received 16 August 1985, accepted 24 December 1985

Some new 2,4,6-trisubstituted-*s*-triazines having carbethoxymethylamino and 4-aminoantipyrine moiety have been prepared. The constitution of the products is supported by ir and nmr spectral study.

SEVERAL workers have investigated *s*-triazine derivatives as potential therapeutic agents for diseases due to bacteria and protozoa¹, African sleeping sickness^{2,3}, malaria^{4,5}, cancer^{6,7} and possess antiviral property⁸. *s*-Triazine derivatives are also used as fungicides^{9,10} and weedicides¹¹.

In continuation of our work on *s*-triazine nucleus¹² and in order to study their therapeutic utility, we have synthesised substituted *s*-triazine derivatives of type 1 and 2 (where R=aryl) by condensing glycine ester hydrochloride and 4-aminoantipyrine with 2,4-diarylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine as they are having therapeutic importance.

2,4-Diarylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine^{5,9,13,14} have been prepared by condensing cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) with different bases (0.02 mol) in acetone at 35-40° for 1.5 h. The third chlorine of cyanuric chloride was condensed with glycine ester hydrochloride or 4-aminoantipyrine in dioxane by heating

at 85-90° for 1.5 h. The structure of the compounds synthesised were supported by ir and nmr spectral study. The ir spectra were taken on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer using KBr pellets in the range of 4 000-600 cm⁻¹. It gave following characteristic bands: 820 (C₃N₃)¹⁵, 1 255 (C-O-C str ester), 1 238 and 1 050 (C-O-C str Ar-O-CH₃), 3 400 and 3 260 (N-H str), 1 660 (C=O), 780 and 715 cm⁻¹ (C-H bending monosubstituted benzene). The nmr spectra were taken on a EM-360 60 MHz spectrometer using CDCl₃ and DMSO as solvent. It gave the following T value:

2.3-3.1 (m, Ar H), 6.8 (s, N-CH₃) and 7.8 (s, C-CH₃).

Experimental

2,4-Diphenylamino-6-carbethoxymethylamino-*s*-triazine: 2,4-Diphenylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in dioxane (30 ml) and to it was added a solution of glycine ester hydrochloride (0.01 mol) in dioxane. The mixture was neutralised by adding sodium hydroxide solution. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (90%), m.p. 202° (Found: C, 62.57; H, 5.38; O, 8.69; N, 22.7. C₁₅H₂₀O₂N₆ calcd. for: C, 62.64; H, 5.49; O, 8.79; N, 23.08%).

Similarly all other 2,4-diarylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine were condensed. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

4-(2',4'-Diphenylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)aminoantipyrine: 2,4-Diphenylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) was dissolved in dioxane (30 ml) and to it was added a solution of 4-aminoantipyrine (0.01 mol) in dioxane. The mixture was refluxed for 1.5 h. The acid evolved was neutralised by adding sodium hydroxide solution. The product was isolated and crystallised from ethanol, (90%), m.p. 263° (Found: C, 66.25; H, 5.27; O, 3.48; N, 24.57. C₂₅H₂₄ON₈ calcd. for: C, 66.37; H, 5.31; O, 3.53; N, 24.77%).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF 2,4-DIARYLAMINO-6-CARBETHOXYMETHYLAMINO-5-TRIAZINE

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	M.p. °C	Nitrogen % Found/(Calcd.)
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆	69	180	22.70 (23.08)
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆	72	145	21.22 (21.48)
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆	67	118	21.30 (21.48)
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆	75	174d	21.23 (21.48)
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆	70	150	19.73 (19.81)
6.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆	66	210	19.69 (19.81)
7.	<i>p</i> -Carbethoxyphenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₆	60	188d	16.41 (16.53)
8.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ Br	59	198d	15.95 (16.09)
9.	α -Naphthyl	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₆	60	191	17.90 (18.10)
10.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ Cl	62	193	19.32 (19.44)
11.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ Cl	60	189	19.25 (19.44)
12.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ Cl	65	218	19.35 (19.44)
13.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆	72	190d	24.59 (24.67)
14.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆	61	>360	24.62 (24.67)
15.	<i>p</i> -Acetylphenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₆	60	212	18.69 (18.75)

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF 4-(2',4'-DIARYLAMINO-5-TRIAZIN-6'-YL)AMINOANTIPYRINE

Sl. no.	R	Molecular formula	Yield %	M.p. °C	Nitrogen % Found/(Calcd.)
1.	Phenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ ON ₆	90	268	24.57 (24.77)
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ ON ₆	87	162	22.45 (22.76)
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ ON ₆	80	190	22.53 (22.76)
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ ON ₆	91	200	22.65 (22.76)
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₆	85	138	21.15 (21.37)
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₆	89	218	21.21 (21.37)
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₆	79	198	21.25 (21.37)
8.	<i>p</i> -Carbethoxyphenyl	C ₂₇ H ₃₂ O ₄ N ₆	82	242	18.35 (18.42)
9.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ ON ₆ Br	71	186	17.21 (17.33)
10.	α -Naphthyl	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ ON ₆	76	207	19.76 (19.85)
11.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ ON ₆ Cl	84	147	20.86 (21.05)
12.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ ON ₆ Cl	81	244	20.73 (21.05)
13.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ ON ₆ Cl	86	225	20.92 (21.05)
14.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₁₀	83	>360	25.15 (25.27)
15.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₁₀	87	231	24.91 (25.27)
16.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₁₀	78	216d	24.95 (25.27)
17.	<i>p</i> -Acetylphenyl	C ₂₇ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₆	70	215d	20.32 (20.43)

Similarly all other 2,4-diarylamino-6-chloro-s-triazines were condensed. The physical constants are recorded in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for awarding Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (L.M.) and to Saurashtra University for facilities.

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